

LIFE PREDICTION OF ANTI-CORROSIVE GLASS FIBER REINFORCED UNSATURATED POLYESTER IN WATER AND ACID

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SAMMARY: The demand for FRP structure having longer life, such as 50 or 100- year life has been increasing. In order to guarantee the long life, two things have to be needed. One is the understanding the degradation behavior and the other is the development of life prediction method. The degradation behavior of the anti-corrosive glass fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester has been studied by some of the authors and it was clarified that the degradation of interphase was the more important factor than the resin and the reinforcement. Therefore we should develop the life prediction method including the interphase degradation. For life prediction, time temperature superposition principal method using stress relaxation test is applied. FRP in pipe configuration for sewage application was tested in water and acid environment. The materials used are the unsaturated polyester and ECR type glass fibers and fabricated by a filament winding method. The deformation was kept constant and the load was monitored for one week in a water bath at the constant temperatures. The acid solution (1N H₂SO₄) and the pipe were put in the polyethylene bag and then sunk in the water bath under acid conditions. The time temperature superposition principle was applied to the result of the stress relaxation test, and the smooth master curve could be obtained in both the water and acid environments. The stress relaxation behaviors in water and acid were the same. The properties in 100 years could be predicted from the master curves. The relationship between the sift factor and reciprocal of the temperature were the Arrhenius type, and the activation energies in water and acid were the same. It means that the stress relaxation behavior in acid could be understood from that in water. Furthermore, the time needed for the test is only for one week, and it is apparently shorter than the previous method for the current life prediction which takes more than one year. In addition, in order to understand the effect of interphase degradation on the stress relaxation behavior, the stress relaxation test for the specimens which have interphase degradation was carried out. The stress relaxation behaviors of the virgin specimen and the degraded specimen were different and the change of the stress of the degraded specimen was larger. It suggests that the stress relaxation behavior would be changed at the time when the interphase damage appears. For further life prediction, this knowledge should be included.

KEYWORDS: GFRP, Life Prediction, Stress relaxation test, Time-temperature superposition principal

1. INTRODUCTION

Glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP), which has high corrosion resistance, has been used as vessels, pipes for chemicals. Recently the application to infra structure is being a focus for GFRP. The GFRP should be used as maintainable materials as a contrast of recyclable materials. In order to use GFRP in infra structure, it is extremely important to guarantee the

long life. However, the knowledge of degradation behavior in GFRP is still poor for accurate life prediction, because the history of GFRP is very short comparing with metals. The life prediction method to guarantee the safe use of products, the knowledge of the degradation behaviors is mandatory.

The life prediction method of GFRP pipe for sewerage application in Japan is established for E glass fiber reinforced plastics which has different degradation pattern from C or ECR glass fiber reinforced plastics used in current sewerage pipe. This is due to the lack of the knowledge of degradation behavior in C and ECR glass fiber reinforced plastics. We have been developing a new life prediction method for C and ECR glass fiber reinforced plastics under acid conditions. The important things for the development are accuracy and quickness. As mentioned above the current method is for E glass fiber reinforced plastics, and of course, accuracy is not enough. The current method requires 12000 hours to obtain data. It would disturb the quick merchandizing of the products. We adopt stress relaxation test to obtain the modulus in service, and time-temperature superposition principal is applied.

When GFRP is used in water and acid environment, the interphase degradation should be considered. Interphase degradation would appear in shorter period than matrix resin and reinforcement. Hence the interphase degradation definitely occurs during long-term use, so that the effect of interphase degradation on lifetime needs to be included in order to aim the accurate life prediction.

In this paper, the life prediction method of the GFRP pipe we developed was presented, and stress relaxation behavior of specimens which have interphase damage was investigated in order to discuss the effect of interphase degradation on lifetime.

2. Materials and experimental

2-1 Stress relaxation test of pipes

In FW-GFRP pipe, isophthalic based unsaturated polyester resin was used as matrix and ECR-glass fiber as reinforcement fiber. The winding angle of this pipe was ± 10 degree, the number of layer was 7, and the fiber volume fraction was 40%. The dimensions of these pipes were as follows; internal diameter was 200mm, thickness was approximately 4.0mm, and width of the pipe was 50mm. The sewerage pipe was generally designed under the permission deflection ratio at 5%. The deflection ratio is determined by dividing applied the deflection by the internal diameter of the pipe. In this study, the stress relaxation test was carried out under the deflection ratio at 2.5%, 5.0% and 10%. The stress relaxation test was carried out in 30°C, 50°C and 70°C under water and 1N sulfuric acid conditions. First, GFRP pipe was set on the stress relaxation testing machines. The testing machines and the pipes were put in a constant temperature water bath. After one hour, the deflection ratio of 2.5%, 5.0% and 10% was applied to the pipe, and the change of load was measured for a week. In testing under the acid conditions, the pipe and the sulfuric acid were put in the polyethylene bag. The edge of the pipe was exposed to the acid solution.

2-2 Stress relaxation test of the specimen with interphase damage

Matrix resin used was vinyl ester (R806; Showa High Polymer, JAPAN), and ECR glass woven fabric (NCR WRE570B100HS; Nittobo, JAPAN) was used as reinforcement. These were laminated by a hand lay up method in 3mm thickness. The specimens were subjected to the pressure cooker test at 2.25atm and 123°C for 10 hours. After the pressure cooker test, stress relaxation test by three point bending mode was carried out at 30, 50, 60, 70°C. Deformation of 5mm was applied and the change of the load was monitored for 7 days.

3. Results and discussions

3-1 Life prediction of GFRP pipes under acid and water condition

The left side of figure 1 shows the results of the stress relaxation test under water and acid conditions at the deflection ratio of 2.5, 5.0 and 10% at 30°C, 40°C, 50°C, 60°C and 70°C. Here,

the load was transformed to the stiffness in accordance with JIS7035. The stiffness decreased in terms of time, and when the temperature rose, the stiffness decreases more. The stress relaxation behavior of both water and acid conditions showed similar tendency. Next, time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) was applied. The data for the reference temperature $T_0=30^\circ\text{C}$

Figure 1 Master curve under water and acid conditions.

were held fixed, and the other curves (40°C , 50°C , 60°C , 70°C) were shifted horizontally along the time axis until the points coalesce to the single curve. Thereby a smooth curve, so called master curve, is obtained as shown the right side in figure 1.

Figure 2 shows the relationship between time-temperature shift factors $aT_0(T)$ when shifting the plots horizontally and reciprocal of the absolute temperature $1/T$ under water and acid conditions. As shown in this figure, the shift factors of water and acid conditions represent one linear line, and they agree well with Arrhenius equation. The calculated activation energy ΔH was 273kJ/mol .

By using the master curves, the stiffness during long-term use could be estimated. Therefore, it can be evaluated whether the property is strong enough in 50 years for example. Each stress relaxation test requires only 7 days in this method, so that the time for the life prediction is clearly shortened comparing with the current method requiring 12000 hours. Furthermore, the

Figure 4 E/E₀ as a function of logarithmic time in water at 50°C

water and acid because the anti- and there would be different degradation patterns or behavior in water and acid condition at under water

ation, however, it will be needed for these stress tests to include the interphase behavior, the damage was

subjected to

3-2 Stress with interphase

Fig. 3 shows the stress relaxation behavior and the specimen modulus. The debonding is clearly observed in the bending stress-strain curve. Fig. 4 shows the modulus at 50°C at different specimen ages more than

Figure 5 Master curves of virgin and PCT specimens.

in addition, the Fig. 5 presents the master curves obtained by time-temperature superposition principle. It is apparent that the decrement of the modulus of the specimen with interphase damage was large. From this result, it is suggested that the stress relaxation behavior change in long-term use, and it should be included when predicting the mechanical properties in long-term use. For example, the interphase degradation definitely occurs very early stage [1], so that the prediction including the behavior with interphase damage should be used. In order to do so, the time when the damage occurs need to be understood.

4. Conclusions

Figure 3 Cross section of specimens of virgin and after PCT for 10hr observed by SEM.

A life prediction method of the GFRP pipe was presented, and stress relaxation behavior of specimens which have interphase damage was investigated in order to discuss the effect of interphase degradation on lifetime. The change in mechanical property in long-term service could be predicted by stress relaxation test and time-temperature superposition principle for GFRP pipe in acid and water condition. Furthermore, the stress relaxation behavior of the specimen with interphase damage was investigated in order to include the effect of interphase damage on the change in mechanical property. The mechanical property of the specimen with interphase damage decreased more than the virgin specimen.

References

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